

DEVELOPMENT OF A SCOUTING BOT FOR DEFENCE AND FOREST AREA PROTECTION

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Abstract – It is not possible to monitor the risky and confidential areas like military bases where there is no reach of humans. Also, in unsafe places like jungles with the risk of getting attacked by wild animals, it is very difficult to observe the activities related to poaching or animal trafficking. Where humans can't reach, it's very difficult to know the atmosphere of such risky and hazardous places, that's why taking any steps or entering the area gets risky. In such cases, spy bots can be a relevant help for defense areas and forest area protection purposes. We are proposing a spy bot that can measure or scan a defense or forest area remotely using a lidar sensor and can also send real-time video and audio recordings to the user. The use of lidar sensor in this project is to know about the area for surveillance in low-light conditions. The structure of this bot is like a quadruped spider which will help us to conduct surveillance in rough and hilly areas.

Keywords – Quadruped, Surveillance, Defense, Spybot

1.0 Introduction

In this paper, we have presented a surveillance robot in which we have used Arduino NANO and ESP32 CAM as microcontroller that will help us in surveillance and the controlling of this robot can be effortlessly managed via Wi-Fi robotic controller software that will be installed in the user's smart phone. According to nowadays technologies, many types of wireless connections like GSM, GPRS, Wi-Fi, WLANs, and Bluetooth can be used among which Wi-Fi and Bluetooth are the most common connections. In this robot, we have used Arduino NANO which will have an in-built Wi-Fi communicator in it using which they can easily control the robot according to their own convenience. This robot will be having a quadruped spider-like structure. It will have 4 legs in which 3 servos motors will be connected to each leg. The Servo motors will get instructions from the Arduino NANO and work according to the user-given instructions. Instructions are given to the robot through the smart phone app via way of means of the users.

2.0. Components used in this project:

1. Arduino NANO
2. Arduino NANO Expansion Shield
3. ESP32-CAM Module
4. Lidar Sensor
5. HC-05 Bluetooth Module

6. SG90 Servo Motors
7. Power Supply
8. Jumper Wire
9. 3D Printed Bot Structure
10. Switch
11. Pan Tilt Servo Setup
12. Buck Converter
13. Microphone

3.0. Methodology:

3.1. Block Diagram of Movement Part of the Robot:

Figure 1: Block Diagram of Robot Movement

This is the block diagram of the movement of this spider robot. Here, we have used Arduino Nano as a microcontroller which is designed using Arduino IDE software. The HC-05 Bluetooth module will receive the commands given by the user from his controller and pass them to Arduino Nano. Then the Arduino Nano will process the commands and run the servo motors accordingly. The HC-05 Bluetooth module will be connected to the user's controller via means of the smartphone app.

3.2. Block Diagram of Surveillance Part of the Robot:

Figure 2: Block Diagram of Surveillance Part of the Robot

According to the above block diagram, the ESP32-CAM Module captures the real-time video and sends it to the device where the user can observe the surveillance, and a power supply is attached to the ESP32-CAM Module. It delivers power to the module as well as the whole system.

3.3. Circuit Analysis:

3.3.1. Circuit Diagram of Movement Part of Spider Robot:

This is the schematic diagram for this Bluetooth Controller spider robot's movement mechanism using Arduino NANO. There are 4 legs, in which 3 servos are connected at each leg. Total 12 servo motors are used in the movement function. These 12 SG90 Servo motors are connected to Arduino NANO Expansion Shield in which the Arduino NANO is placed. The Arduino NANO is connected to the phone via HC-05 Bluetooth Module. The user gives instructions through the phone which are transmitted to Arduino NANO. As a result, we get the wanted movement of the robot.

Figure 3: Circuit Diagram of Movement Part of Spider Robot

3.3.2. Circuit Diagram of Surveillance part of Robot:

Figure 4: Circuit Diagram of Surveillance part of Robot

To develop the surveillance part, we used a servo motor to move the neck and face of the robot. We have used ESP32-CAM Module and the attached camera as the visual sensor and a Microphone as the sound sensor. ESP32-CAM Module is connected to a power supply to power the whole circuit.

4.0. Results:

The project has been finished with success with the utmost satisfaction. The project gives a clever plan for growing a full-fledged utility fulfilling the person's needs. This device is extremely versatile. Provisions are created to improve the code. It has been examined with live records and has supplied a prosperous result. Then the code has been tested to determine expeditiously. The device created met its objectives, with the aid of using being truthful to apply. This code is advanced with measurability in mind. Further modules can't be really different as soon as necessary. The code is advanced with a popular approach. However, there is nonetheless plenty of scope for future development and accessories in practicality. It is displaying live video footage to the user's device and the motion of the robot is likewise great.

6.0. Applications and Future Scope of the Project:

- This robot can be used as a surveillance device in military areas and forest bases.
- This robot can run on hilly and rough surfaces easily as it has the structure of a spider.
- It can be made waterproof and climbable on tall objects.
- It will contain a foldable propellor which will help it travel long distances in a short period of time.
- It will be having self-defense mechanisms in it too for its own safety.

7.0. Conclusion:

To develop this project, we have learned Arduino IDE Programming. With the success of this project, we would like to continue our research work in this field and develop much more advanced robots which can solve real-life problems. In the end, we would like to thank our mentor Ms. Susmita Das Madam for her great contribution in our project. Without her guidance and support, this project wouldn't become a success.

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